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THE IMPACT OF TRANSFORMATIONAL AND SPIRITUAL LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEE WORK PERFORMANCE: MODERATION SPIRITUALITY IN THE WORKPLACE

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the effects of transformational leadership and spirituality at work on employee performance as well as the moderation of spirituality at work on the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance. This study is a quantitative study conducted at PT. Vale Indonesia Tbk. The number of study participants is approximately 353 employees and students using questionnaires as a data collection method. The data analysis methods used in this study are regression analysis using the line regression and regression analysis using SPSS version 23. The study's findings indicate that transformational leadership has a significant impact on employees' work habits, spirituality at work has a significant impact on employees' work habits, and spirituality at work moderates the impact of transformational leadership on employees' work habits. Practical implication is the leaders must apply spiritual leadership principles in day-to-day management, such as providing emotional support and motivating employees with positive vision, as well as fostering spiritual and emotional well-being. Motivation has a significant impact on employees' work performance. Consistent implementation of the motivational program will ensure that the strategies implemented have a positive impact on the increase in employee productivity.

KEYWORDS: Leadership, Transformational, Spirituality, Employee, Performance.

JEL: M12, M14, M54.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today's business environment is increasingly unpredictable and dynamic. Leaders play a crucial role as drivers of innovation and change within organizations, as they are largely responsible for developing a vision, determining the necessity of change, and implementing it (Gilley et al., 2009; Tayal et al., 2018). However, leadership efforts may fail due to inadequate leadership practices and ineffective change management (Judge, 2011; Lei et al., 2019). Transformational leaders, in particular, encourage followers to embrace change strategies and motivate them to exceed expectations in achieving organizational goals by fostering trust (Islam et al., 2021).

There has been extensive discussion regarding leadership styles that effectively facilitate organizational change, making the relationship between leadership and change one of the most debated topics in organizational studies (Burnes & By, 2012). Change itself is described as a sequence of events occurring within an organization that requires employee support and commitment to ensure the success of change initiatives (Yasir et al., 2016; Tayal et al., 2018).

Transformational leadership is a well-established concept in management literature (Riggio & Bass, 2006; Son et al., 2020). It refers to leaders who clearly communicate organizational goals, act as catalysts for change, actively coach employees, inspire them to develop new skills, and continuously seek opportunities for organizational growth. In today's rapidly evolving business environment, transformational leadership has become one of the most effective leadership approaches, contributing to significant and positive organizational outcomes (Tayal et al., 2018; Pasamar et al., 2019; Son et al., 2020).

Workplace spirituality refers to a shared sense of purpose and connectedness among employees, where individuals experience meaning and enthusiasm in their work. Employees who are more engaged and passionate tend to generate better ideas and contribute more effectively to organizational goals. According to Ashmos and Duchon (2012), workplace spirituality reflects employees' awareness of an inner life that nurtures meaningful work. It allows individuals to integrate their personal values with their professional roles, fostering a sense of connection, wholeness, and purpose (Pandey et al., 2013).

Initially, workplace spirituality received limited attention from researchers and practitioners. However, over the past two decades, interest in this

area has increased significantly (Ananda et al., 2022; Putra et al., 2022). The growing number of publications, conferences, and academic discussions indicates that workplace spirituality has become an important topic in organizational research (Rana et al., 2020).

Previous studies have shown that workplace spirituality enhances employees' adaptability, encourages change-oriented organizational citizenship behavior (Sulastini et al., 2023), promotes creativity (Ranasinghe & Samarasinghe, 2019), and improves productivity (Wahib & Machfudz, 2023). Furthermore, adopting positive work attitudes supported by strong spiritual values contributes to organizational growth (Risgiyanti et al., 2020). Employees increasingly seek meaningful work by integrating spiritual values into their professional lives (Ahmed et al., 2022). Moreover, organizations with higher levels of workplace spirituality tend to achieve greater success, faster growth, and improved efficiency (Garg, 2020; Garg et al., 2022; Al-Mahdy et al., 2022).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Employee Performance Concept

Employee performance, according to Lutfi (2023), refers to the outcomes of a specific work process that can be evaluated within a given period based on predetermined standards and agreements. The concept of employee performance has evolved alongside the development of human resource management, influenced by advancements in science and technology as well as ongoing research.

This evolution is consistent with Edison's (2020) perspective, which builds on Miner's (1998) concept that employee performance has shifted from a focus on time utilization to the achievement of work outcomes. Furthermore, Edison (2020) emphasizes that adherence to organizational values is a crucial dimension of employee performance.

2.2. *The Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Employee Performance*

Transformational leadership focuses on the relationship between leaders and followers, which is grounded in shared needs, values, and beliefs (Buil et al., 2019). Leaders who adopt this style strive to help followers understand their roles, needs, and objectives within the organization. By aligning employees' values with organizational goals, leaders can enhance overall work performance (Campbell, 2017).

This leadership style is also associated with higher levels of psychological empowerment. In such conditions, employees are less driven by monetary considerations and more motivated by intrinsic factors related to their roles. Therefore, it is important for organizations to understand how transformational leadership fosters psychological empowerment (Mufti et al., 2019).

Moreover, effective transformational leadership has been shown to improve employee performance and encourage employees to prioritize organizational interests over personal goals (Rasdi et al., 2020). Empirical evidence, such as studies conducted on Chinese nurses, also supports the positive impact of transformational leadership on performance (Kwon & Choi, 2020).

Based on the theoretical and empirical evidence above, it can be concluded that transformational leadership has a significant relationship with employee performance.

H1: Transformational leadership has a significant effect on employee performance.

2.3. The Relationship between Workplace Spirituality and Employee Performance

Workplace spirituality is an emerging concept in organizational behavior and management studies, particularly within the context of organizational culture. It is often associated with values, ethics, and meaningful work experiences.

According to Milliman et al. (2003), workplace spirituality consists of three main dimensions:

1. Meaningful Work

This dimension refers to employees' ability to perceive meaning and purpose in their work. It reflects how individuals experience their daily tasks as significant and valuable.

2. Alignment with Organizational Values

This dimension represents the compatibility between employees' personal values and the organization's mission and goals. It emphasizes the importance of shared values and a sense of contributing to a greater purpose.

3. Sense of Community

This dimension focuses on the quality of relationships among employees, including a sense of belonging, connection, and mutual support within the workplace.

Workplace spirituality reflects the awareness that employees have an inner life that is nurtured through meaningful work within a supportive community. Organizations that promote spiritual values recognize that employees seek purpose, connection, and fulfillment in their professional roles.

When employees' spiritual values align with organizational goals, they are more likely to find meaning in their work, which in turn enhances their performance (Marwan et al., 2020). Previous research also confirms that workplace spirituality has a significant positive effect on employee performance (Marwan et al., 2020).

H2: Workplace spirituality has a significant effect on employee performance.

H3: Workplace spirituality moderates the effect of transformational leadership on employee performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

This type of research uses a quantitative methodology that focuses heavily on data collection, classification, comparison, and analysis. It also tests hypotheses with numerical research variables, compares them, and then conducts statistical data analysis. The dependent variable is employee performance, while the independent variables in this study are transformational leadership and spirituality in the workplace. The goal is to figure out how these factors influence the dependent variables. The study's population includes all employees who work at PT. Vale Indonesia Tbk. This research uses non-probability sampling with the help of the Slovin formula to determine the number of samples used in this research. From a population of 3.023 employees using the Slovin Formula, there are 353 employees in the sample.

Because the information was gathered directly from respondents via a survey in the form of a questionnaire, this study uses primary data. The survey was created as a Google form and disseminated to 353 respondents online via WhatsApp and other social media platforms. Because the information was gathered directly from respondents via a survey in the form of a questionnaire, this study uses primary data. The survey was created as a Google form and disseminated to 353 respondents in PT. Vale Indonesia Tbk. Of the 353 questionnaires distributed, 327 questionnaires could be processed for research data. Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA), commonly referred to as the interaction test, was the analysis method used with the SPSS 23 software. MRA is a particular type of multiple linear regression where interaction components are incorporated into the regression equation.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Result

Since each variable's mean is greater than its

standard deviation, as determined by descriptive statistical analysis, each data point for each variable is shown equally.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistic.

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Transformational Leadership	327	2,94	4,83	4,1050	0,2728
Spirituality in the Workplace	327	3,00	4,70	4,0766	0,3387
Employee Performance	327	2,60	4,90	4,0829	0,4043

The descriptive statistics indicate that the data are relatively homogeneous, as reflected by the low standard deviation values. Furthermore, the normality test result (Sig = 0.074 > 0.05) confirms that the data are normally distributed. Furthermore, A validity test is performed in order to confirm the statement's credibility. If the r count result is greater than the r table, the questionnaire is deemed valid for this study. Transformational leadership and spirituality in the workplace variables on the questionnaire are all considered as valid since their average r counts are greater than the r table (0.165). To ascertain a questionnaire's dependability based on

the research variables, a reliability test needs to be conducted. The Cronbach Alpha (α) technique was used to assess reliability in this study. We can conclude that all seven variables have Cronbach Alpha values greater than 0.6. As a result, this research survey can be deemed credible. After determining the validity and reliability of the research data, conventional assumptions such as normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity are tested. Table 2 displays the results of the heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, and normality tests.

Table 2: Results of the Classical Assumption Test.

Testing	Testing Value		Summary
Normality	Sig = 0,074		Normally Distributed Data
Multicollinearity	Tolerance	VIF	Non-Multicollinearity
Transformational Leadership	0,989	1,011	
Spirituality in the Workplace	0,989	1,011	
Heteroscedasticity	Significance		Non Heteroscedasticity
Transformational Leadership	0,083		
Spirituality in the Workplace	0,888		

The determination coefficient (R²) test seeks to quantify the degree to which the independent variables impact the dependent variable. The determination coefficient (R²) test result is 0.531. The coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.531, indicating that 53.1% of the variance in employee performance is explained by transformational leadership and workplace spirituality. The remaining 46.9% is

influenced by other variables not included in this study. Ghozali claims that, under the assumption that all other variables remain constant, the t-test is used to demonstrate the degree to which each independent variable influences the dependent variable. The hypothesis is accepted if the sig number is less than 0.05.

Table 3: Hypothesis Testing Results (t-Test).

Variable	Coefficients	Std. Error	t-count	Sig.
Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance	0,265	0,075	4,298	0,000

Workplace Spirituality on Employee Performance	0,072	0,017	3,521	0,001
Moderation of Workplace Spirituality on the Relationship between Transformational Leadership and Employee Performance	0,363	0,113	3,208	0,002

The test results in Table 3 support the study's conclusion that transformational leadership influences employee performance. Hypothesis 1 is approved. According to the study's findings, workplace spirituality influences employee performance. Hypothesis 2 is approved. The study's findings show that workplace spirituality moderates the effect of transformational leadership on employee performance. Thus, Hypothesis 3 is approved.

The moderation analysis shows that workplace spirituality significantly strengthens the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance ($\beta = 0.363$, $p < 0.05$). This indicates that the positive effect of transformational leadership on employee performance becomes stronger when employees experience higher levels of workplace spirituality. In other words, workplace spirituality enhances the effectiveness of transformational leadership by providing meaning, value alignment, and a sense of community among employees.

4.2. Discussion

4.2.1 The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Employee Performance

These findings suggest that transformational leadership plays a critical role in enhancing employee performance by fostering motivation, trust, and psychological empowerment. When leaders effectively communicate vision and support employee development, employees are more likely to exceed performance expectations.

The study by Kwon & Choi (2020), which claims that transformational leadership significantly improves performance, is consistent with these findings. Additionally, these findings support earlier research by Rasdi et al. (2020), which found that transformational leadership improves worker performance. Since many employees disagree that leaders support employees' courage to voice their opinions, focus on their professional growth, and consider their needs while they are working, transformational leadership has little effect on employee performance.

The results of the analysis demonstrate that the variable of transformational leadership has contributed to a rapid increase in performance. This

condition can be explained as follows: as transformational leadership increases, performance will also rise noticeably. Inspiring pride in subordinates, impressing them, explaining strong goals, considering the implications of each decision, applying pressure to the work community, being optimistic in conversations about the future, talking enthusiastically about work, articulating the belief that goals can be achieved, seeking differences in perception to solve problems, persuading employees to solve problems from various perspectives, suggesting new approaches to solving problems, interacting with people other than group members, paying attention to the needs, aspirations, and abilities of subordinates (employees), and supporting their development are all demonstrated by superiors using a transformational leadership style.

4.2.2 The Influence of Spirituality in the Workplace on Employee Performance

Employee performance is significantly impacted by spirituality in the workplace, according to research findings. (Banuari, 2023) defines workplace spirituality as having a transcendental relationship with God, understanding the meaning of work on an individual basis, being enthusiastic about work based on spiritual values, feeling comfortable at work, having good relationships with coworkers, and focusing on organizational goals. According to Srivastava and Pradhan (2021), workplace spirituality can be defined as an individual's endeavor to live out spiritual values at work or as an organization's endeavor to cultivate a passion for work based on spiritual values, establish harmonious and ethical working relationships, concentrate on organizational goals, have a transcendental relationship with a higher power, and have a sense of justice and compassion. The application of spiritual values in the workplace can work in tandem with the organization's objectives to foster employee creativity and maximize profitability. It is also very helpful in establishing peaceful and productive working environments. Several earlier studies have noted the impact of workplace spirituality on employee performance, including those by Hafni et al. (2022). The most important impact of workplace spirituality on employee performance, according to research (Mousa, 2020), is alignment with

organizational value dimensions. Researchers came to the conclusion that the significance of spirituality in the workplace improves the organizational environment, especially at the organizational and workgroup levels within the company, based on the aforementioned studies. Research (Siregar & Rambe, 2022) states that there is an influence of spirituality in the workplace on performance.

4.2.3. The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Employee Performance Moderated by Spirituality in the Workplace

Workplace spirituality is found to significantly moderate the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance. The positive coefficient indicates that workplace spirituality strengthens the effect of transformational leadership on employee performance. This suggests that when employees experience a higher level of meaning, value alignment, and sense of community at work, the effectiveness of transformational leadership becomes more pronounced. In other words, transformational leadership yields stronger performance outcomes in environments where workplace spirituality is high.

Workplace spirituality has a big impact and mitigates the impact of transformational leadership on output. This is demonstrated by the way employees interpret their work in light of a set of deeply held personal values, which reflects their desire to find meaning and purpose in life. A worship ethic, for instance, serves as the cornerstone and basis for their conduct at work. This is evident in their words and enthusiasm at work, which is shown by positive responses to tasks. This increases employees'

focus and performance by encouraging them to work hard and give their best effort. This is consistent with Hassan, who works in the education sector in Islamabad, Pakistan, and who demonstrates that performance and workplace spirituality are significantly influenced. Furthermore, Hassan adds that if there is a strong spiritual component to the workplace, it will inspire employees to put their best effort into their work, which will lead to excellent performance. Employee spirituality, or the capacity to discover purpose in one's work life, can enhance employee performance. This can be accomplished by fostering collaboration and communication among coworkers. Put another way, meaningful work, a sense of community, and value alignment are the components of spirituality in the workplace.

Workplace spirituality is proposed as a moderating variable in the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance. As a moderator, workplace spirituality influences the strength of the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance. Specifically, a higher level of workplace spirituality strengthens the positive impact of transformational leadership on employee performance. This occurs because workplace spirituality fosters a sense of meaning, alignment of values, and a supportive work environment, which enhances employees' responsiveness to transformational leadership behaviors. In contrast, in environments with low workplace spirituality, the effectiveness of transformational leadership may be less pronounced. Therefore, workplace spirituality plays a critical role in amplifying the effectiveness of leadership in improving employee performance.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model.

Transformational leadership is proposed to have a direct effect on employee performance. In addition, workplace spirituality is positioned as a moderating variable that influences the strength of this relationship. Specifically, workplace spirituality is expected to strengthen the positive effect of

transformational leadership on employee performance. This model suggests that the effectiveness of transformational leadership in improving employee performance will be higher when workplace spirituality is also high.

Furthermore, according to Prihono's research, an

individual's degree of spirituality will enhance their performance as an employee. Understanding the importance of life, or spirituality, will lead to good and sincere behavior in daily life and the conviction that God will provide for our needs. This will boost one's motivation for life and even for work, which will improve one's performance.

5. CONCLUSION

The study's findings suggest that the company's management should prioritize more successful transformational leadership techniques in order to have a positive impact on workers' performance. In the event that this is not feasible, management must also prioritize new transformational leadership techniques that better suit the needs of the workforce. As a result, management needs to instill habits by giving employees briefings and inspiring business

executives to continuously push their staff to boost productivity.

There are some restrictions on this study. First, this study uses the workplace spirituality variable to investigate the impact of transformational leadership on employees' work habits, whether they are subtle or not. Employee work performance may also be influenced by a few other factors, including organizational culture, knowledge management, skills, and motivation. The following research must therefore be understood, looked into, and analyzed. Furthermore, this study is being carried out in mineral companies, which may limit its generalizability to other industries. As a result, there is a great desire to carry out more thorough research on this subject in different industries. It can be applied to any nation or area, or it can be contrasted with small, micro, and medium-sized businesses and large organizations.

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